

Year : 7
Issue : 26
Oct-Dec 2017

www.chintanresearchjournal.com

ISSN : 2249-2976
Price : ₹ 500

Impact Factor : 2.645

(Art, Humanity, Social Science, Commerce, Management, Law & Science Subjects)

(Indexed & Listed at : Ulrich's Periodicals Directory ©, ProQuest. U.S.A.)

(Indexed & Listed at : Copernicus, Poland)

(Indexed & Listed at : Research Bib, Japan)

(Indexed & Listed at : Indian Journal Index (IJINDEX))

(UGC Approved List No. 41241)

(International Refereed)

Pramāna

Research Journal

Editor-in-Chief

Acharya (Dr.) Shilak Ram

Assistant Editor

Aruna Devi

यावत् जीवेत् सुखं जीवेत्

Acharya Academy

Bharat

ISO 9001:2008

- साम्प्रदायिक राजनीति एवं भारत का विभाजन
सुमन रानी 95-98
- Quest for Identity in Githa Hariharan's The Thousand Faces of Life
Sheeta, Dr. Monika 99-103
- Customer Satisfaction towards Vodafone Services: A Study of Youths of Rewari District
Pawan Singh, Devesh Aggarwal 104-111
- Customers Perception and Experience towards Retail Banking : An Emperical Study From Customer Side
Manoj Bansal, Dr. Satinder Kumar 112-118
- A Study of Dynamics of Socio-Cultural Milieu of Slums of Gurgaon
Krishna Devi 119-122
- Contemporary significance of Monism
Ananya K. P. 123-126
- Hurdles to The Road of E-Retailing
Swati 127-134
- 'मैं' और 'परमात्मा'
डॉ. पल्लवी शर्मा 135-137
- विद्यालयीन विषयों का मूल्य संचारण में योगदान का अध्ययन
डा. तरुणा नरुला 138-146
- विवेकी राय के उपन्यासों में पारिवारिक संबंधों का अनुशीलन
डॉ. राजेश कुमार 147-148
- हनुमन्नाटकम् में शक्तित्व की प्रासंगिकता एक अध्ययन
डॉ. मूलचन्द्र 149-153
- उपनिषदों का आलोचनात्मक चिन्तन
प्रो. लवनीन ग़ोवर 154-156
- कबीर काव्य में दार्शनिकता
डॉ. मधु बाला 157-162
- सर्वोदय एवं भूदान आन्दोलन में जयप्रकाश नारायण की भूमिका
सुरेश कुमार 163-170
- मध्यकालीन हरियाणा में सिंचाई व्यवस्था
प्रिति 171-176
- भारतीय साहित्य का स्त्री विमर्श की दृष्टि से अवलोकन
जगमोहन 177-182
- मैक्सिको भूकम्प : एक प्राकृतिक आपदा
रेशमा 183-188
- सरस्वतीकण्ठाभरणस्यालोके चान्द्रव्याकरणस्य लुप्तस्वरवैदिकाध्याययोः पुनरुद्धारः समीक्षणं च
डॉ. रामचन्द्रः 189-193

A Study of Dynamics of Socio-Cultural Milieu of Slums of Gurgaon

Krishna Devi
Assistant Professor
JVMGRR College
Charkhi-Dadri(Bhiwani)

Abstract

Tradition has been a common can widely used theoretical term in social sciences. During the past 20 years the term has attracted renewed interest, especially from anthropologists, ethnologists and historian. This paper examines and reflects the agents of change and their impact. The agents of change being Migration, Urbanization, Modernization and their impact in terms of changes in life style and traditional values. Such as replacing old instruments in Household by modern once, increased use of cosmetics, western clothes and many more are the focus area of this paper. Which are given in the paper in detail.

Key-Words: Traditional values, Globalization, Modernization, and Urbanization.

Introduction

Culturally diverse and complex, with mainly rural, traditional and agrarian population, India is experiences rapid growth and rural urban migration. It is nation undergoing significance social, economic and political change, while at the same time struggling to maintain many of its tradition and customs. The shadows of a vibrant consumer society are taking shapes and urban population is exposed to massive change in life style, consumption habits and cultural conditioning.

Tradition:

Tradition is the accumulated heritage of culture i,e the symbolic culture of group which provide a legitimacy and justification of social order. Tradition is a concept that answers the identity formation.

Tradition can be seen as the transmitted value and behaviour of any community which has been persisting over a period of time. Tradition are respected, exemplified and referred to frequently.

According to Max Radin in Encyclopedia of social sciences, "Strictly and properly speaking a tradition is not a mere observed fact like an existing custom, it is an idea which expresses a value judgment. It produce in a nation or in a group value judgment. It produce in a nation or in a group an exacted group consciousness and is therefore most effective in creating groups or in reestablishing than.

Tradition do not remain static, the old or previous traditions fade away and become extinct and new ones are adopted by a community in due course of time. External as well as internal factors both contribute to the changes in tradition. The various factors exercising key role in change of traditional values and life style can be enumerated as followings:

1. Migration
2. Urbanization
3. Modernization
4. Globalization

Migration

Migration being an important agent in bringing changes in traditional values, the present study examines the same among in women in urban slum in Gurgaon city. It examines the impact on traditional values and lifestyle with rise in migration.

Migration is usually considered an economic phenomenon but it also creates a cultural phenomenon in both homeland and land of destination. Many relationships are torn apart. The folk culture represented by *nautanki*, folk songs and folk paintings which hold a place of importance and shed all together in the process of rural urban migration.

The process of rural urban migration in a developing country has manifested itself in formation of urban slums to a large extent due to high incidence of poverty and inadequate facilities of organizing and rehabilitating the poor and displaced.

The women residing in the urban slums in Gurgaon city have poorer life style, fewer opportunities but a larger family. They struggle to provide their family the basic necessities living in a unofficial unsanitary conditions. All they have is a poorly constructed shack. A large number of family members adjust in small place. They mostly draw water from a single sharred tap. Most of these women being either uneducated or have rudimentary education are unskilled laborers and hence are working as domestic maids. Some also stitch and do embroidery but are able to earn a meager amount of Rs-20/- to 30/- a day.

Urbanization

Urbanization is an index of transformation from traditional rural from traditional rural economies to modern industrial ones. It is progressive concentration op population in urban unit. Urbanization cab be explained as a process of switch from spread out human settlement to one of the concentration in urban centers. It is infinite process through which nation pass as they evolve from agrarian to industrial economy. The phenomenon of squatter settlements has to be seen as a stage is the process of urbanization in the developing country like India. Cities are the end fundamental changes in the society that accompany socio-economic development and modernization.

Urbanization is increasing at a rapid rate as a whole while the health service, employment opportunities and social services are not increasing correspondingly. As such, life style of many households staying in these areas starts deteriorating leading some times the youth to became anti social elements.

Rapid urbanization has lead to alarming deterioration in the quality of life various infrastructural deficiencies, poor sanitation and solid waste disposal, water shortage, polluted natural water resources, water logging frequent epidemics, inadequate health care, depletion of green areas, proliferation of slums. The aggregate impact of distress is specially deliberating of the urban o poor living in slums.

Women and children in the slums are most affected as they continuously manage their daily lives and chores in decaying environment. Unlike men and children, women are more often remain in these surroundings slogging and sweating whole day. She is ignorant about many things including how to guide her children. She need guidance and proper education. The children in slums suffer from parental care. There is absence of any adequate programe to equip her for employment opportunities. Unaided and unguided she suffers, shattering the entire dream of upliftment socially and economically.

Modernization

The advent modernization has bought about a series of major changes in the social structure. Modernization is an interactive process of economic growth and social change. The process of modernization is related to industrialization, urbanization, high standards of livings.

Contemporary Indian society is striving to adopt modernization for economic growth and social change. One of its strongest influences has been the awakening of women's consciousness. With rapid economic development and advent of women's movement the changing status of women received much attention. The role of women began to change from the submissive, traditional women to modern, demanding equal rights sovereignty and independence. The impact of modernization has been significant. On one hand it has opened up economic opportunities in some areas on the other it has led to decline in traditional sources of income for women as those engaged in the production handmade and homemade items. Women have experienced difficulty in acquiring access to credit improved technologies and increased services. As a result, women's production has generally remained at a low level and they have failed to improve upon their status and position.

Globalization

Globalization is the new buzzword that has dominated the world. The frontier of state with increased reliance on the market economy Globalization has brought in opportunities to developing countries. The focus of globalization developing countries not only includes opening data and ideas but also infections diseases, pollution and wider income gaps.

For women, The impact of globalization has been uneven. A small layer have gained work opportunity in term of newly emerging forms of employment, especially in the IT, service and food-processing sector, but the semi/unskilled ones have lost control over their natural resources as well as in traditional industries, resulting in the loss of traditional livelihood and sustainability. Gender is not a homogeneous category, but is interested by class, caste, community and ethnicity and impacted by age, ideology and sexual preference.

In the formal sector women workers have neither contracts nor social security, and have low wages and unhygienic working conditions. Poverty, lack of medical insurance, and forced overtime and the culture of self-denial often make health the first casualty. Women suffer from cases of dehydration and miscarriages are common. The lack of income security for women in the informal sector also means children's lack of access to education. As a result the children also get pushed in to the informal sector themselves.

The worst off among all the unorganized sector women are the women employed across urban India as domestic maids living in slums.

Life style changes

Due to various reasons like modernization, financial constraints and time crisis women living in the urban slum have left many such household chores which once have been very important part of their daily routines. Grinding of spices, wheat and looking after cattle have no more remained a part of their daily lives. They say that it has been years that they haven't used Chakki (grinding wheel). Even they buy the spices directly from market to use. Hookah which was quite prevalent in villages, more among the elderly women is almost extinct.

While mela, nautanki, puppet shows and folk songs have lost their importance malls, cinema halls have gained importance as a mode of entertainment.

An increasing craze of going to beauty parlors is a peculiar change quite noticeable. Women living in slums have become conscious of their looks. Increased use of cosmetics though substandard due to lack of money is very apparent. Tooth Paste, shampoo, cold creams and similar items have replaced the use of traditional products like datoon and mustard oil. This change has largely been due to Television Programs and flooding commercials. Globalization, commercialization and increasing competition has made it possible for women living in such areas to access modern gadgets.

Urbanization, modernization and imitation have also brought a marked change in clothing and food habits. While women in rural areas mostly wear sari with palla on their head or ghunghat, those migrating to cities have started wearing salwar suits. The young girls even wear western outfits like jeans etc.

A significant fact noticed in slums that women are quite aware about rights, privileges and law made for them. They know about APL, BPL ration cards, old age pensions and many such government schemes floated for them from time to time. They know that the legal age to get their daughter married is 18 and marrying them before this age a legal offence. All these facts revealed that women organization working in slums have also played an important role in bringing about a change.

Despite many changes of varied types patriarchy still dominates the lives of women. They are still subordinated to patriarchal set up and lack cultural and social autonomy. Though some minor shift is noticeable due to economic constraints and growing awareness but it cannot be said that women hold a rightful place. On the contrary aspiration to be equal to the upper caste has eroded the cultural autonomy of the lower caste in the sense that blind imitation of upper caste has resulted in loss of their identity.

Reference

1. Davis, K and Golden, H.H/ 1954 Urbanization and development in pre-industrial Areas. Economic Development and Cultural Change 3(1) 6-26
2. Dube, S.C. (1956) India's Changing Villages. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
3. Becker, C.M., Mills E.S. And Williamson J.G. (1986). Modeling Indian Migration and city growth, 1960-2000. Economic Development and cultural change 35(1) : i 33
4. Pandey, Saumyata (2014) Traditional values and life style changes among women in urban slum of Lucknow, Man in India, 94(4):691-702
5. Mitra, A. (1992). Urban poverty: A Rural Spill-over. In Indian Economic Review. V. Pandit and Suresh D. Tendulkar eds. Special no. In Memory of S. Chakravarty.